

Tree root pruning in maize alley-cropping: would it have saved the maize? The Hi-sAFe model answers. Will you believe it?

EURAF 2022
Agroforestry for the Green Deal transition.
Research and innovation towards the
sustainable development of agriculture and
forestry

Corresponding author:
Dupraz Christian

Christian Dupraz¹, Isabelle Lecomte¹, Lory Boutchakdjian¹, Marie Gosme¹, Francesco Reyes¹

¹INRAE, UMR Absys, University of Montpellier, Montpellier, France

Theme: Climate Change (adaptation & mitigation)

Keywords: alley cropping; walnut; modelling; tree-crop competition,

Abstract

In 2021, a maize crop was a total failure in our alley-cropping agroforestry site of Restinclières. The walnut trees are now mature, and capture up to 70% of the incoming radiation during summer months. Maize yield dropped drastically in alley cropping to values below 25% of the monocrop control, for well irrigated, poorly irrigated and non-irrigated maize as well. This relative yield was even less than the relative incident radiation, suggesting that no compensation mechanisms for light limitation were at work. The 2021 summer was however rainy and no heat wave was recorded. In such conditions the climate protection of the maize crop by the trees could not be efficient, and the light competition was probably the dominant mechanism. However, some observations suggested that water competition by the trees was still active, as testified by maize wilting close to the tree rows, even in deep shade.

To explore this issue, we used the Hi-sAFe agroforestry simulation model. After calibrating the maize variety parameters on the monocrop control, we obtained sensible simulations of the alley-cropping system. Then we made a virtual experiment by root-pruning the walnut trees to cancel below ground competition for water and nitrogen between trees and maize. This allowed us to predict what would have happened if we had root-pruned the trees. Other simulations with a dryer and hotter summer helped to understand what would have happened if the weather had been more extreme. This work illustrates the subtle interactions between erratic weather conditions and tree and crop management in silvoarable alley cropping, and the limits of climate change adaptation that can be expected in agroforestry systems.

Figure 1: A maize crop in the deep shade of a mature walnut plantation at Restinclières, France.